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COUPLED PIEZORESISTIVE AND THERMORESISTIVE BEHAVIOR OF CARBON NANOTUBE YARNS AND THEIR THERMOSETTING MONOFILAMENT COMPOSITES

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Carbon Nanotube Yarn for Sensing in Composite Materials

(a) Tall CNT forest. (b) CNT forest (array). (c) CNT thread being drawn. (d) CNT thread being in spool. (e) One-thread yarn (diameter of 8 μm, angle of 8.9°). (f) Two-thread yarn (diameter of 11.6 μm, angle of 8.1°). All materials provided by Nanoworld Laboratories at University of Cincinnati.

• Carbon nanotube yarn (CNTY) can be used as piezo-impedance-based sensors (impedance, Z , and resistance, R).

$$Z(\omega) = Z_{real} + jZ_{imag} = R + j\left(\omega L - \frac{1}{\omega C}\right)$$

Sensing Concept Features

- Distributed Sensing
- Integrated Sensing
- Microstructure Integrity
- Real-Time Data Collection
- Minimal Additional Weight

Study geared towards developing strain and temperature sensors

Experimental Setup/Results and Data Analysis

Optical image of the experimental setup including an instrumented CNT yarn sample in the card loading fixture that is mounted in the loading machine and connected to the LCR meter.

(a) Schematic of monofilament composite sample for thermoresistive testing (current, I , voltage drop, V). (b) Optical image of corresponding sample.

Coupled characterization of CNT yarns and monofilament composites. (a) Piezoresistivity of free CNT yarn and polymer-embedded CNT yarn (monofilament composite). (b) Corresponding thermoresistivity curves.

- The piezoresistive sensitivity is given by the gauge factor (G_F): $\Delta R/R_0 = G_F \epsilon$ where $\Delta R = R - R_0$ is the variation of electrical resistance, R_0 is the initial electrical resistance (unloaded at room temperature), ϵ is the applied strain (values at Anike, J. C. et al. /C/ 2017, 3(2), 14).

- Linear thermoresistivity is given by $\Delta R/R_0 = \beta \Delta T$ where β is the thermoresistive sensitivity and ΔT is the temperature variation ($-88.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for CNT yarn and $-65.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for CNT yarn monofilament composite).